

7th International Conference on Renewable Energy and Conservation, ICREC 2022 November 18–20, 2022, Paris, France

Dealing with change: Retraining strategies to improve load forecasting in individual households under Covid-19 restrictions

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Received 14 August 2023; accepted 27 August 2023

Available online 5 September 2023

Abstract

Covid-19 pandemic and the restrictions imposed to control its spreading had a profound impact on several aspects of society. Studies on energy consumption show a pattern shift during the first stages of the pandemic, mainly due to the abrupt and forced change in human behaviour. For some residential consumers, such changes translated into higher energy expenses, which could be avoided through optimal energy management. This, however, depends on accurate load forecasting models whose performance tends to decrease under drastic pattern changes. This paper aims to improve forecasting techniques based on machine learning methods to assess its impact on the accuracy of day-ahead electrical load forecasting from individual residential households from the city of Barcelona, Spain, during a lockdown situation. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is the proposed algorithm for the short-term hourly forecasting of the households' electricity consumption of the following 24 h. The algorithm's accuracy over different pandemic periods – Lockdown, Reopening and New Normal – is evaluated using different retraining strategies based on literature findings.

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Peer-review under responsibility of the scientific committee of the 7th International Conference on Renewable Energy and Conservation, ICREC, 2022.

Keywords: COVID-19; Energy demand; Residential load; Load forecasting; Time series; Support vector machine; Machine learning; Clustering

1. Introduction

In early 2020, COVID-19 became one of the world's biggest concerns as the virus started spreading globally and impacted, directly or indirectly, all existing sectors. In the energy arena, the restrictions imposed on citizens and businesses to control the virus spreading drastically changed electricity generation and consumption patterns, especially at early stages when strict lockdowns were imposed in different countries [1]. In Barcelona, Spain, three different periods can be identified during the pandemic based on the implementation and lifting of restrictions imposed by the Spanish authorities as a result of the COVID-19 emergency: lockdown, reopening and new normal. The total lockdown period is the most disruptive and significant to study and analyse pattern changes, as during this time the city saw a decline of its total electricity consumption between 10 and 35% [2].

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Under pandemic conditions, households are an interesting case of study as Covid-19 policies significantly impacted socioeconomic and living patterns [3]. In particular, transitory curfews and restrictions together with the popularization of teleworking increased the amount of time that people spend at home [4], translating into higher electricity demand. For some consumers, new electricity consumption patterns meant higher electricity expenses, which negatively impacted their economy and put those in vulnerable conditions at higher risk of energy poverty. This is a worrying side effect of the pandemic, particularly considering the increased unemployment rates observed during this period in countries like Spain [5].

A possible solution to avoid or mitigate the extra costs associated with an increased electricity demand is the use of self-consumption and Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) to optimize their electrical load during changing demand and price conditions [6]. Nonetheless, to perform optimally, HEMS rely on accurate load forecasting algorithms, whose functioning is also altered by the drastic pattern changes induced by COVID-19 [7]. It is then pertinent to research strategies that might help systems to cope with this circumstances if similar events take place in the future.

1.1. Load forecasting under COVID-19

Machine learning methods have become popular techniques for electrical load forecasting, including both residential and non-residential users, as the implementation of smart meters has spread among different regions, allowing access to detailed historical consumption data. Their usage has demonstrated to be particularly useful for forecasting electrical consumption at the aggregated level, but their potential application in individual residential or commercial users has also been validated in previous research such as [8]. This is particularly interesting in Spain, as it is one of the leading countries in Europe in the usage of smart meters in residential households [9].

Some of the most used models within this field are Neural Networks, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), regression, clustering, and Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) [8]. As they all rely on the assumption that future energy use will behave similarly to past consumption data, their performance suffers under drastic pattern changes, such as those experienced during COVID-19, as this assumption is no longer valid. This situation is known as “concept change” or “concept drift”, which is defined as changes in the conditional distribution of output given the input, and is one of the major challenges for machine learning methods [10].

Potential modifications to solve the concept drift challenge in the forecasting of electrical loads under COVID-19 conditions have been studied by different authors. Nonetheless, most of these focused on aggregated loads, for instance at the regional or city level. This is the case of the work performed by [11,12], where the inclusion of new features – mobility and pandemic data (e.g. infection rates) – into machine learning models were tested for different regions in Europe and the United States of America. The authors of [11] also analysed the effect of using only weekend’s pre-pandemic data as training input for the models, obtaining significant improvements in their model’s performance.

At the individual level, fewer examples are found, particularly dealing with residential users. The most relevant is the research conducted in [13], which looks at the effects of the pandemic on day-ahead residential load forecasting, testing the performance of two regression type models – based on K-nearest neighbours (KNN) – in 10 households in Madrid, Spain. For the top performing variant, the authors also test the effect of using only lockdown consumption data instead of all historical values to retrain the model during the pandemic, improving its accuracy metrics. Other interesting examples are conducted by [14,15], which study the performance of Neural Networks models – Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) – on individual commercial users. In the first case, the model is adapted by introducing a simplex optimizer for the training parameters, which improves the model’s performance when few historical data are available, for instance, at the beginning of the pandemic if features such as infection rates are to be included. The second uses online learning and different learning rates to allow the LSTM model to adapt to the consumption changes reported in an office building in California, USA during different pandemic stages.

1.2. Main contributions

The present article aims to add knowledge to the understanding of the effects of drastic consumption changes in individual residential electricity consumption forecasting. To do so, it analyses the performance of a state-of-the-art

machine learning model (SVM) in predicting the day-ahead consumption of individual residential loads from the city of Barcelona, Spain. SVM was chosen over other time series forecasting algorithms because it can effectively overcome the shortcomings of traditional prediction models (e.g., weak classification ability and over-fitting), and is widely used in load forecasting applications similar to the analysed in this paper [16]. As the novel features proposed in some of the literature are not as relevant for individual users as for aggregated loads [17,18], different retraining strategies are selected as adaptation measure to COVID-19 conditions based on the work of [13]. These are implemented and tested during different pandemic stages according to the methodology explained in the next section.

2. Methodology

As the goal is to test the performance of forecasting model adaptations under pandemic conditions, a pre-pandemic week and three pandemic stages identified for the city of Barcelona are used as testing periods. The duration and main characteristics of each stage are described below:

- Pre-pandemic (2nd March 2020 – 8th March 2020). A pre-pandemic week is considered for comparison purposes.
- Lockdown (28th March 2020 – 03rd May 2020). All services are closed except for emergency and essential goods providers. Remote learning and teleworking is implemented. A strict curfew is imposed around the clock, and only essential tasks are permitted outside (e.g. grocery shopping).
- Reopening (04th May 2020 – 19th June 2020). Emergency and non-essential services gradually re-open. Remote learning and teleworking are still the norm for most jobs and educational levels. The curfew is gradually relaxed, lowering limitations for leisure activities, especially during the last phases.
- New normal (20th June 2020 – 07th August 2020). All services providers are open, including non-essential, but social distancing rules are still observed on a changing basis. Schools and non-essential work places are open.
- Teleworking continues being popular fully or on a hybrid work modality. Curfews are implemented when infection rates grow, but only at night.

2.1. Load data description

Hourly electricity consumption from 1st January 2018 to 31st December 2021 is obtained from a sample of 1400 residential consumers from a specific retailer in Barcelona, Spain. This covers pre-pandemic data used for typical model training, as well as the pre-defined pandemic stages. Users' data is recorded by smart-meters and downloaded through the retailer's Application Programming Interface (API).

The sample is built by randomly selecting 40 households from each of the 35 postal codes in which the utility has over 40 active contracts. Personal information, such as customer name or full address is left out to ensure anonymity. The contracts are classified in quintiles based on their total annual consumption. Two households from each quintile are then selected, obtaining a total of 10 households. Fig. 1 shows the steep increase in consumption during lockdown and how similar the aggregated 10 households sample is to the total residential load in the city.

Fig. 1. Comparison of the aggregated load of the 10 selected households and the total of the residential sector in Barcelona during 2020.

Table 1. Selected features used in the SVM algorithm.

Type	Features
Meteorological	Temperature Precipitation levels
Date index	Hour of the day Day of the week Holidays
Historical consumption	Last 120 h demand

2.2. Load forecasting algorithm

A day-ahead forecasting algorithm is built using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) model. SVM is a machine-learning method developed from the structural risk minimization principle and statistical learning theory [19]. This feature model can nonlinearly map the training data from a low-dimensional plane to a high-dimensional space [20]. The application of SVM is quite extensive and includes time series forecasting and analysis, classification and regression clustering [21].

Feature selection: The features used in the proposed model are listed in Table 1. These correspond to typical parameters for electrical load forecasting in residential applications [6]. In particular, weather and historical electrical demand seem to be widely used in the literature [22].

2.3. Evaluated retraining strategies

The performance of the developed SVM model is tested using three different training strategies. The Benchmark strategy consists of using historical data from 2018 and 2019, without retraining periodically. This single-trained strategy is a usual setting used to reduce forecasting times when predicting electricity loads with machine learning algorithms [23]. Applying this strategy on the proposed case studies means that pandemic behaviour is not included in the training set, which is expected to result in worst forecasting performance during the pandemic stages.

Fig. 2. Retraining strategies evaluated in the SVM forecasting model.

As observed in Fig. 2, two alternative strategies with periodical retraining are tested for comparison. Strategy 1 retrains the model weekly using 1 year of data, whereas the Strategy 2 also retrains weekly but using only the last 30 days previous to the beginning of the forecasted horizon. Weekly retrains are used in HEMS application to better capture differences in consumption behaviour as exemplify in [24]. In most cases, at least a year of historical data is provided for training. However, Strategy 2 uses a shorter time span, following a similar approach to that proposed by [13], where only consumption data during the pandemic is used to forecast households' load at this period. This is expected to have a positive impact during the Lockdown stage, but its applicability during Reopening and New Normal periods remains to be tested.

Performance metrics: To assess the performance of the model using the retraining strategies proposed the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is selected, as it is the most common metric used to forecast electrical energy

Table 2. Households' electricity demand and contracted power.

Users	Contracted power (kW)	Annual demand 2019 (kWh)	Annual demand 2020 (kWh)
U1	8.80	5051.83	5582.34
U2	3.45	3998.58	4077.72
U3	4.40	1884.30	2146.01
U4	4.40	1935.93	1944.37
U5	6.60	2031.28	1788.70
U6	4.40	1708.99	2457.25
U7	4.40	1639.51	1755.31
U8	3.30	1207.94	1550.82
U9	5.75	1141.24	1267.65
U10	3.50	1242.28	1246.66
Average	4.90	2184.19	2381.68

demand [25].

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

3. Results

The main characteristics from the households selected as a result of the process described in Section 2 are presented here. Table 2 summarizes the contracted power and the annual electricity demand for 2019 and 2020 for each selected household. For contracted power, the most common value is 4.40 kW. In general, annual consumption increased in 2020 compared to 2019, which could be explained by the longer hours that people spent at home due to COVID-19 restrictions. Regarding the average hourly consumption for 2020, most of the households used between 0.18 and 0.24 kWh during this year, with values somehow in compliance with contracted power.

3.1. Retraining strategies performance

In this section, the accuracy of the implemented forecasting method and its retraining strategies proposed in the methodology are evaluated and discussed. The RMSE obtained from the Strategy 1 is similar to the Benchmark strategy. The average RMSE of all 10 households is 1.05% worse during Pre-pandemic week when using Strategy 1, but RMSE improves 2.5% during Lockdown. These results might indicate that during periods where consumption patterns are stable, using periodical retraining is not necessary, especially if it implies longer forecasting times. However, as conditions change and patterns are altered, periodical retraining is beneficial to the algorithm's performance. This is particularly visible during the Lockdown week in which more drastic restrictions were put in place.

Regarding Strategy 2 – which implies training with the last month of data and therefore uses data that is labelled inside the same forecasted period – the algorithm performance significantly improves during the Lockdown week. For this period, the RMSE values obtained using Strategy 2 is 5.7% better than the Benchmark strategy. Notably, Strategy 2 translated into better forecasting accuracy for eight out of ten users during this period compared to the Benchmark training strategy. For some specific users, such as U6, this improvement can be as high as 13%. On the other hand, the periods of Reopening and New Normality see an average error increase of 2.4 and 8.2% respectively. Moreover, only four users in Reopening and one in the New Normal stage get more accurate forecasts than when using the Benchmark strategy. Thus, the results indicate that the strategy proposed by [13] only reflects in better accuracy metrics when applied during Lockdown period, but does not work optimally when consumption patterns starts to behave similar to before the disruptive event. It must be noted that this retraining strategy only uses 30 days of data for training, so even though it retrains weekly, the computational effort that carries is much lower and it fits the model much faster than the other two strategies.

The following graphs show an example of how the retraining strategies impact on the forecasted values obtained during Lockdown and Pre-pandemic weeks. This example is a clear residential case where the pattern consumption changes considerably during Lockdown in comparison to pre-pandemic days. This key factor favours a retraining

Fig. 3. Retraining strategy performance (U4, Lockdown).

Fig. 4. Retraining strategy performance (U4, Pre-pandemic).

strategy with shorter training data but regular retraining to outperform standard strategies with longer training periods. During the Pre-pandemic example, the strategies with more training data (Benchmark and Strategy 1) show better results, but during Lockdown, the strategy with shorter training periods (Strategy 2) offers the best fit. In particular, for user U4, Strategy 2 results in a 12% RMSE improvement during Lockdown (Fig. 3) than when using the Benchmark strategy (Fig. 4). This improvement is not observed in the Reopening and New Normal stages.

4. Conclusions and future work

In order to execute real-time functional and optimal HEMS strategies, a reliable and accurate forecast of short-term load electricity demand is needed. In this paper, two retraining strategies have been deployed and evaluated on top of the Benchmark strategy (2-year historical data) set for the proposed SVM algorithm: Strategy 1 (weekly retraining with one-year data) and Strategy 2 (weekly retraining with 30-days data). They are all explained in Section 2.

The SVM algorithm is proposed as it provides adequate results for the problem of forecasting electricity consumption as shown by previous research. The accuracy of the forecast has been tested in 10 different households located in Barcelona, Spain, and their performance has been evaluated based on the RMSE metric.

The results obtained for Strategy 1 show that retraining periodically does not significantly improve the forecasting accuracy when consumption follows a stable pattern, for instance, during the pre-pandemic period. However, when conditions change drastically – such as in the pandemic stages – its usage might be justified as it offers better accuracy than the Benchmark case. For Strategy 2, the results obtained are promising during the Lockdown period, as it shows a significant global improvement of 5.7% in comparison to the Benchmark strategy, which is significantly higher than for Strategy 1. Moreover, eight out of ten users show improved forecasting metrics using this strategy during the Lockdown period, with 13% being the highest individual improvement found. However, its usage resulted

in worst RMSE metrics for the rest of the evaluated periods, including the Reopening and New Normal stages, in which conditions were still not fully the same as in pre-pandemic times.

The COVID-19 pandemic changed users' electricity consumption habits, which led to a degradation in the performance of forecasting models. This is understood as the concept drift problem and the models had to be retrained. The results obtained show that the retraining of SVM models using only data from the disrupting periods, such as Lockdown, has the potential to improve the model's accuracy during events with similar characteristics. However, its accuracy is lower for other periods where the alterations are not as drastic (as observed in the results for Reopening and New Normal periods). This particular strategy is cost-effective in terms of computational power as it only uses 30 days of data to retrain the algorithm. However, its application might be limited to disruptive events and not recovery and post-recovery stages, which then poses the challenge on real applications to identify the transition from one period to another.

In future work, the impact of COVID-19 on the studied households' electricity bills will be estimated. For those households experiencing higher electricity expenses, the potential to minimize energy costs usage of a HEMS optimizing the operation of a PV-coupled battery system will be analysed using the forecasting model and the retraining Strategy 1 presented in this paper.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Mariana Jimenez Martinez reports financial support was provided by Catalan Agency for Management of University and Research Grants (AGAUR). Eric Pla reports financial support was provided by Catalan Agency for Management of University and Research Grants (AGAUR).

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the Agency for Management of University and Research Grants, Spain (AGAUR for its Catalan acronym) for awarding an aid under "Pandemies 2020" call for the project "ComMit-20 – 2020PANDE00116" with the support of the Secretariat for Universities and Research of the Department of Business and Knowledge of the Generalitat de Catalunya, used for the funding of this research.

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